

The Condensation of Aldehydes with Malonic Acid in Presence of Organic Bases. Part I. In Presence of Pyridine alone.

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The condensation of aldehydes with malonic acid has been extensively studied using such condensing agents as alcoholic ammonia, primary and secondary amines, particularly piperidine (Knoevenagel, *Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 2596 *et seq.*), pyridine (Verley, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1899, **21**, 143; Doebner, *Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 2140; 1901, **34**, 53; 1902, **35**, 1136, 2137; Staudinger, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1927, **41**, 440), pyridine with a trace of piperidine (Haworth, Perkin and Rankin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 1693; Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **1**, 297), and other secondary and tertiary bases (Dalal and Dutt, *ibid.*, 1932, **9**, 309).

In this paper various aldehydes, particularly the aromatic hydroxyaldehydes, which gave poor or no yield with pyridine alone, have been condensed with malonic acid and a trace of pyridine.

The condensation of salicylaldehyde with malonic acid could be expected to give three possible products: *o*-coumaric acid (I), coumarin carboxylic acid (II) and coumarin (III).

It has been found that the condensation proceeds only when a trace of pyridine is present (*vide* Experimental) and gives 51% of coumarin carboxylic acid (II), m.p. 187-89° as was obtained by other methods (Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, **32**, 389; Stuart, *ibid.*, 1886, **49**, 366 and Knoevenagel, *ibid.*, 2585, 2593) and not *o*-coumaric acid (I) m.p. 200°, as reported by Dutt (*loc. cit.*).

The other aldehydes that could be condensed in the same way are mentioned in the Experimental part.

EXPERIMENTAL.

(K. C. PANDYA AND V. R. SURANGE).

In the first experiments pure dried malonic acid (3 g.) was condensed with molecular proportions of aldehyde and of the carefully purified pyridine (3 c.c.), by heating on a boiling water-bath for about 4 hours. The product on cooling was treated with sodium carbonate solution and steam-distilled, the residue acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the precipitated acid purified by crystallisation.

TABLE I.

Aldehyde condensed.	Acid obtained.	Yield.	Duration of heating.
Benzaldehyde	Cinnamic acid	83%	4 hrs.
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	<i>o</i> -Nitrocinnamic acid	96	2
<i>m</i> - " "	<i>m</i> - " "	93	2
<i>p</i> - " "	<i>p</i> - " "	90	2
Salicylaldehyde	None	0	18
Vanillin	"	0	6

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Condensation of salicylaldehyde with malonic acid: Formation of coumarin carboxylic acid.—After various trial experiments using different quantities of pyridine at varying temperatures and changing the duration of heating, the following condition gave the maximum yield of the condensation product.

Salicylaldehyde (6 g.) and malonic acid (5 g.) were heated together for 4 hours on the water-bath. Pyridine (0.5 c.c.) was then added, the flask cooled, and the whole left at 15° for 5 days. The flask was then again warmed at 60-65° for 4-5 hours. The acid then separated in the usual way, m.p. 187-89°. (Found: C, 62.79; H, 3.31. $C_{10}H_6O_4$ requires C, 63.15; H, 3.16 per cent). The silver salt gave an equivalent weight 190.3, while Dutt's acid (I) requires 164 and $C_{10}H_6O_4$ requires 190. The melting point never rose above 189° and it was depressed to 160-65° by admixture with an

authentic specimen of *o*-coumaric acid (I). On heating it gave the smell of coumarin and not of phenol and its barium salt was insoluble.

Ferulic acid.—Vanillin (3.1 g.), malonic acid (2.1 g.) and pyridine (0.3 c.c.) were mixed and heated on a water-bath for 4 hours. On cooling the solid was powdered, shaken with chloroform or treated with sodium carbonate solution and the clear solution acidified with hydrochloric acid. On recrystallisation from water, it melted at 169°, and with solutions of ferric chloride, silver nitrate, lead acetate and Fehling's solution respectively, gave the characteristic reactions of ferulic acid, yield 4 g. (57%).

p-Hydroxycinnamic acid (*p*-coumaric acid).—*p*-Hydroxybenzaldehyde (2.4 g.), malonic acid (2 g.) and pyridine (0.8 c.c.) were heated in the usual way for 5 hours. From the liquid product, *p*-coumaric acid, m. p. 207°, was obtained in 33% yield.

m-Nitrocinnamic acid.—*m*-Nitrobenzaldehyde (3 g.), malonic acid (2 g.) and pyridine (0.2-0.3 c.c.) were mixed and heated for 4 hours, within half an hour a solid was formed and the acid melting at 198° came out in 92% yield.

p-Methylcinnamic acid was obtained from *p*-tolualdehyde (2.3 g.), malonic acid (2 g.) and pyridine (0.2-0.3 c.c.). It melted at 198°, yield 84%.

Cinnamylidenemalonic acid and cinnamylideneacetic acid.—
(a) Cinnamic aldehyde (3 g.), malonic acid (2.4 g.) and pyridine (3 c.c.) were heated on a water-bath for 1 hour. The solid was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution, the solution acidified when cinnamylidenemalonic acid, m.p. 208° (decomp.) was obtained, yield 90%.

(b) In another experiment the heating was continued for 18 hours and cinnamylideneacetic acid, m.p. 165°, was obtained, yield 50%.

β-Benzylcrotonic acid, prepared from hydrocinnamic aldehyde (2.6 g.), malonic acid (2 g.) and pyridine (0.2-0.3 c.c.) by heating for 4 hours, melted at 104°, yield 29%.

p-Methoxycinnamic acid.—Anisaldehyde (3.4 g.), malonic acid (2.6 g.) and pyridine (0.2-0.3 c.c.) were heated for 4 hours. It melted at 172°, yield 78%.

Piperonylacrylic acid.—Piperonal (3 g.), malonic acid (2 g.), pyridine (0.2-0.3 c.c.) were heated for 4 hours. It melted at 240° (decomp.), yield 100%.

Furfurylacrylic acid.—Freshly distilled furfural (2.3 g.), malonic acid (2.5 g.) and pyridine (0.2-0.3 c.c.) were heated on a water-bath, the mass immediately turned brown and began to solidify after 3 hours' heating. Heating was continued for 2 hours more, the product separated and purified by crystallisation from hot water, m. p. 136°, yield 73%.

Trichlorocrotonic acid.—Chloral (2.83 g.), malonic acid (2 g.), pyridine (0.3 c.c.) were heated on a water-bath at 85° for 5 hours. On cooling a solid separated, which on purification melted at 119°, yield 28%.

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